

Dissemination and communication guide

Addressed to Beatriu de Pinós fellows

beatriu
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Communication and Dissemination Guide

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Agency for Management of University and Research Grants (AGAUR)

Ministry of Business and Knowledge, Government of Catalonia

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1. Why communicate and disseminate your research?

Dissemination and communication activities, including public outreach, are part of the Beatriu de Pinós fellowship and complement the execution of the research project.

When writing a proposal, dissemination and communication activities are often considered as a formal requirement. However, if these activities are properly planned and executed, they will **help to increase the impact of research** in many ways and will contribute to researchers' professional development. Strategic communication and dissemination actions can, for instance, help to increase research funding in one field, establish new contacts in both academia and business environments, and foster further research by opening new questions.

Sometimes there is some confusion about what the words “communication” and “dissemination” mean. The following table (adapted from The European IPR Helpdesk, 2018¹) is an introduction to clarify the terminology. Some examples of their corresponding activities will be described in chapters 2 and 3 of this guide.

	Communication	Dissemination
Focus	Inform about and promote the project and its results .	Describe results available for others to use.
Objective	Reach out to society and show the impact and benefits of research activities, e.g. by addressing and providing possible solutions to fundamental societal challenges.	Transfer knowledge with the aim to enable others to use and take up results, thus maximising the impact of research.
Target audience	Multiple audiences beyond the project's own community, including media and the broad public .	Audiences that may take an interest in the potential use of the results (e.g. scientific community, industrial partners, policymakers).
Timing	Starts at the outset of the project.	Starts when results are available.

¹<https://www.iprhelpdesk.eu/IP-Highlights/brochure>

Despite these differences, the boundaries between certain activities are blurry or can overlap. For instance, a web post highlighting the project and its achievements that was originally written for communication purposes could end up in the hands of potential stakeholders and trigger their interest in using some of the results.

Communication and dissemination actions should be understood as **transversal issues** that complement research and training activities throughout the **whole project's life cycle**. Communication activities will go hand in hand with the research activities throughout its duration, while activities related to dissemination of results become more relevant towards the end of the project and continue even after the project is finished.

The communication and dissemination plans included in the proposal must be **regularly reviewed and adapted** to suit possible circumstances that were not foreseen at the beginning of the research project. Besides, the impact obtained should be regularly assessed to check whether the planned objectives are being achieved. BP fellows must report all the communication and dissemination activities carried out during the project in the final report.

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1.1 Benefits for your research project

- **Increase the visibility** of your research and enhance your reputation by presenting your work and its results to the scientific community, to potential industrial and academic partners, to policymakers and to society at large.
- Let citizens know **why public resources are spent in research** and how this can improve their daily lives in the future (solving societal challenges, creating new jobs, improving knowledge, leading to new technologies, influencing changes in policies, etc.)
- **Secure funding** in your research area and reach potential additional funding sources, by drawing the attention of governments and private stakeholders to the need and benefits of your research.
- Encourage talented students and scientists to get involved in a **scientific career**.
- **Discover novel approaches**, solutions and challenges by promoting the exchange of knowledge at cross-sectoral and interdisciplinary levels.
- **Attract potential users** of the project results and generate market demand for the products or services developed.
- **Trigger new collaborations** and opportunities for you and your research team.
- **Improve your score in scientific assessments**, as these increasingly include mentions of your publications in communications tools, such as social media, blogs, etc.
- Progress in your **professional development** by acquiring new skills related to communicating results, adapting your vocabulary to a target audience, interacting with stakeholders, etc.

1.2 Contractual commitments

Several communication and dissemination-related commitments for BP fellows are formally outlined in documents such as the **call terms** and the **call announcement**. The following table includes a summary of all these commitments, some explanatory notes and the reference to legal texts for further information (valid for 2018 and 2019 calls).

Communication

The proposal must include a communication plan that describes the activities addressed to non-specialized audience.

General terms and conditions, Article 12.

Fellows must follow the requirements of the European Charter for Researchers. This includes the public engagement principles.

General terms and conditions, Article 17.1 | The European Charter for Researchers (European Commission): <https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/jobs/charter/european-charter>.

The beneficiary institution must include the relevant emblems (Ministry of Economy and Knowledge of the Government of Catalonia emblem and European Union flag) on its website .

Opening call for applications, Article 8.

Throughout the fellowship period, the BP fellows and the beneficiary institutions must promote communication activities addressed to the public and the media, and acknowledge the financial support by the Government of Catalonia and the European Commission.

Opening call for applications, Article 8.

Dissemination

The proposal must include a dissemination plan that describes the activities addressed to the members of the scientific community and to other potential stakeholders who may be interested in using the results.

General terms and conditions, Article 12.

Fellows must follow the requirements of the European Charter for Researchers. This includes the dissemination and exploitation of results principles.

General terms and conditions, Article 17.1 | The European Charter for Researchers (European Commission): <https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/jobs/charter/european-charter>.

Academic publications, as well as data and results obtained in the research project, must be deposited in an open access repository. Open access dissemination of results may be restricted for reasons involving security, privacy, personal data protection or commercial/industrial exploitation, but these exceptions must be justified and notified in advance to AGAUR.

General terms and conditions, Article 17.

In publications or in other context in which results are shared, BP fellows must acknowledge the support received from the Beatriu de Pinós Programme, the Secretariat of Universities and Research (Government of Catalonia) and the European Union (grant agreement No 801370).

Opening call for applications, Article 8.

Complementary allowance

The BP grant includes a supplementary amount which may cover expenses related to communication and dissemination activities, including attendance to conferences, journal publication fees, data preservation in repositories, training in related issues and the purchase of consumable supplies and materials that may be used in outreach activities.

General terms and conditions, Article 5.

1.3 RRI and Open Science

As a BP fellow, you must be familiar with the most relevant principles related to **Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI)** and **Open Science**.

RRI involves societal actors working together all over the whole research and innovation process in order to better align both the process and its outcomes with the values, needs and expectations of society. It is based on 6 key points:

- Engagement of **all societal actors**: researchers, citizens, policy makers, companies and civil society organisations.
- **Gender equality** in human resources management and R&I content.
- **Science education** to improve the understanding of science by citizens and to promote research as a career choice.
- **Open access** to research results of publicly-funded projects.
- **Ethics** as a basis for increased social relevance and acceptability of research.
- **Governance** actions to align RRI principles within organisations.

RRI principles are present in the definitions, goals and criteria of the **UE framework for research and innovation** (Horizon 2020 and the forthcoming Horizon Europe) and are gradually being incorporated into national and regional R&I policies in European countries. To become a successful researcher, you should be able to embed RRI principles in your research strategy and in your professional development as a horizontal issue.

In the context of RRI and good research practice in general, **openness and transparency** are fundamental. In order to benefit the society, the products of your research must be disseminated to stakeholders and communicated to all societal actors. In this sense, the European Commission promotes the concepts of **Open Research** and **Open Access**, which mean that all project results and data should be made accessible, so they can be found and re-used by other researchers, innovators or other societal actors. Thus, further research is encouraged, novel solutions can be found, and the use of results becomes more efficient.

2. Communication

2.1 Strategic planning: the communication plan

The strategic planning for communication actions begins at the proposal stage of the project. However, the initial communication plan is not definitive; it will evolve and must be updated throughout the project lifetime. If you draft the communication actions in advance and align them with specific objectives, they will provide much more impact and visibility for your research project.

Some useful **steps** that you can follow to **create a communication plan** are listed below:

- **Analyse your project:** what do we already know about the issue? Which problems will your research solve? Which results are expected? How could your research impact society?
- **Define communication objectives** (specific and measurable) that stem from the overall project objectives.
- **Define the audiences** you want to reach. Try to target homogeneous groups of people: instead of targeting “the media” or “the public”, define a more specific target group, for instance “female European teenagers who use social media”.
- **Formulate a key message** for each target group, using words that can be understood by non-specialists.
- **Check the communication services** offered by your institution and the outreach initiatives that are regularly organised in your surroundings (press offices, corporative blogs with dissemination purposes, science fairs, outreach programmes in schools or high-schools, etc.). Assess whether by joining these activities you can achieve your objectives and reach the target audiences, or else you need to set up new initiatives.
- Choose the right communication activities and means and include specific **timelines and deadlines**.
- Describe how you will document, **evaluate and report** the communication activities.

Communication is a work in progress, but some **good opportunities** can help to maximize the impact, for instance if:

1. You are going to publish a research paper in a major journal.
2. You have obtained a highlighted result, have developed a new method or have tested a new technology.
3. You have created interesting audio-visual material of your project (images, videos, interactive content, etc.)
4. Your research is related to current news.
5. You have been awarded a scientific prize.
6. You are going to be part of a scientific expedition or to engage in an important international consortium.
7. You start a collaboration with the industry or with other non-academic partners.

Formats of communication activities

One-way communication: mass-media (magazines, radio, TV), press-releases, blog posts, websites, videos, brochures, posters, handbooks, etc.

Two-way communication: social media debates, school visits, open days, workshops, science fairs, focus groups, roundtables, demonstrations, questionnaires and surveys, etc.

2.2 Tips for engaging your audiences

- **Focus on your audience's interest:** what do they already know about the topic of your project? What is their opinion about it? How can your project change their everyday life? Which are the main benefits of your project for society?
- **Tell a story,** don't just list data or facts. Focus on your personal experiences as a researcher, explain the difficulties that you experienced and how you solved the challenges you encountered in your project.
- **Focus your efforts on a specific audience,** you can't reach everyone. A clear focus will contribute to maximize the impact and will help you to create a message adapted for your target audience.
- Seek **support from professional communicators.** They can give you advice about selecting the most suitable outreach activities or can help you to adapt the vocabulary so it can be easily understood.
- Be creative and **use attractive audio-visual material.** Reduce the amount of text in your presentations, blog post or brochures and focus on images instead. Use videos and infographics in social media.

2.3 Beatriu de Pinós' communication channels

The Beatriu de Pinós team at AGAUR has set up several communication channels and outreach activities to help you to communicate your project. These support tools aim to supplement the services offered by the communication teams from host institutions (universities, research centres...). If you would like us to help you to spread your project, do not hesitate to contact us (BP.postdoc.agaur@gencat.cat).

► Outreach events

The BP team will organise outreach activities to promote the interaction of researchers with citizens. One of these initiatives will allow BP fellows to visit high schools to give short talks or workshops and encourage teenagers' interest in science. Further information about these activities will be provided by BP team.

► Website

The Beatriu de Pinós website² contains news related to the programme and information about calls, the BP fellows and their research projects. In this website you can also find the documents to manage the BP grant, training and professional development opportunities, and useful resources to communicate your research.

► BP Research blog

As a BP fellow, you are encouraged to write a post about your research project in the blog "BP research" on the BP website³. Posts should be easy to understand by a large audience. They can focus on a research result, on a new technology or methodology, or on collaborations with industry or policy-makers. You can also write a post analysing current news related to your area of expertise. Blog posts will be promoted through social networks.

■ Social media

The BP team has created a hashtag for news and events related to Beatriu de Pinós programme: **#postdocBP**. You can use it on Twitter or Instagram to tag your publications related to your research or to your daily life as a postdoc. We encourage you to share content in social media such as attractive or striking pictures about your project, your participation in conferences, scientific publications, outreach activities, etc. If you would like to increase your impact, you can contact us by email and we will spread the information through our official accounts (@recercat and @EuraxessCat).

■ Communication toolkit

On the Beatriu de Pinós website you can find a list of useful online resources to improve your communication skills. It is not an exhaustive list, but it can be a starting point to draft your communication plan. Check whether your university or research centre has institutional communication guidelines or can provide further assistance.

Besides, we will list interesting outreach events on the Beatriu de Pinós website which you can join to communicate your research. The most important events will also be announced on the regular newsletter addressed to BP fellows.

■ Success stories booklet

At the end of the BP project, which is funded by the European Union's Research and Innovation Programme Horizon 2020 (MSCA - COFUND actions), AGAUR will issue a booklet to highlight some of the results obtained in fellows' projects. If you have published in major research journals or have participated in a successful knowledge transfer project to non-academic partners, please contact us and tell us about your success story as a BP fellow.

²www.beatriudepinos.cat

³www.agaur.gencat.cat/Beatriu-de-Pinos/divulgacio/blog-BP

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3. Dissemination

3.1 Strategic planning of dissemination activities

Similarly to communication activities, dissemination activities are planned when writing the project proposal, but should be continually reviewed and adjusted. Throughout the project's lifetime, market needs or potential stakeholders may change, and unforeseen results may be achieved.

To maximise the dissemination of your project's results, you should define a coherent **strategy for knowledge management** and choose effective dissemination channels according to the potential stakeholders. In this regard, you may find the following tips useful:

- Assess the **“state of the art”** and gather information about the current knowledge on your topic (mainly scientific literature, but also patents, related technologies, policies etc.). Identify potential competitors and possible collaborators.
- Analyse who the **potential users** of your project results are, and which are their needs and demands.
- Identify the **key project results** and evaluate potential barriers for their further use (ethical, privacy, safety or security issues).
- Develop a **data management plan** aligned with FAIR principles (see section 3.3).
- Outline the significance of your project in terms of **policy making** and think about specific measures to bring it to the attention of decision makers at regional, national and European levels.

Examples of dissemination activities:

- Scientific publications
- Poster and oral presentations at conferences
- Datasets on data repositories
- Book chapters
- Cross-sectoral secondments and collaborations
- User workshops and demonstrations
- Training and teaching materials
- Participation in brokerage events and investor pitches
- Policy briefs and recommendation reports
- Research stays

3.2 Open Science

Providing **free online access to project results** is the most effective way to ensure that such results can be accessed, read and reused as the basis for future research and innovation. The Beatriu de Pinós programme endorses the values of Open Science promoted by the European Commission and strongly encourages BP fellows to provide open access to their research results.

Intellectual Property issues

Open Access will not affect the intellectual property of your research results. You may choose to publish your results after applying IP protection (for instance, a patent). Similarly, the author retains the publications' copyright even in open-access publications. Thus, the protection of research results and their commercial exploitation is still guaranteed.

a) Open Access to peer-reviewed publications

As stated in the terms of the BP call, open access of scientific peer-review publications related to BP funding is mandatory. There are two options:

- **Green Open Access (self-archiving)**: the final peer-reviewed publication is deposited in an online repository of choice, as soon as possible and no later than 6 months after the official publication date (or 12 months in social sciences and humanities). If the publisher does not accept this condition and only in exceptional cases, a longer embargo period can be accepted (you must contact the BP team at AGAUR to justify this cases).
- **Gold Open Access (open access publishing)**: open access to the peer-reviewed publication is provided immediately by the publisher, often by paying a fee. Note that a copy of the publication must still be deposited in a repository to comply with EC Open Access policies.

To deposit the publications, BP fellows must choose an **OpenAire-compatible repository**⁴, because these repositories allow linking the publications to Horizon 2020 funding. In the Annex of this guide you will find a list of institutional repositories in Catalonia which are OpenAire-compatible.

Open access policies by publishers around the world and **self-archiving permissions given to authors** may be found on SHERPA RoMEO website⁵. Some journals do not accept archiving the final publisher's version of the publication in an open repository, but they allow authors to archive the final draft (after the peer-review process) in order to comply with open access requirements.

b) Open Research Data

It is **highly recommended** to provide open access to data underlying the scientific publications, as well as any other research data generated during the project. Whenever possible, **data should be deposited in a repository** of choice to enable third parties to access, mine, exploit and disseminate data. However, the publication of data may be incompatible with the protection of personal data or with the commercial exploitation of results. In these cases, it will be appropriate for researchers to delay or limit access to data. These exceptions should be planned in advance and reported in the **data management plan**.

⁴<https://explore.openaire.eu/search/content-providers-table>

⁵www.sherpa.ac.uk/romeo

3.3 Data management plan and FAIR data

“As open as possible, as closed as necessary”

The **Data Management Plan (DMP)** is the document that defines the procedures involved in capturing, managing, storing and publishing the research data throughout the project's life cycle and beyond. The DMP is a living document that evolves with the project and should provide information on the following:

- The **data** to be collected, processed or generated: data sources, size, general description...
- The **methodology and standards** that will be applied: format, metadata...
- How data will be **shared**: access to data and possible restrictions, licencing, timing for data sharing, persistent identifier...
- How data will be **curated and preserved**: long-term access, ensuring data integrity...
- How data will be **handled** during the project and after the project is over: procedures, roles and responsibilities, suppliers...

Several **DMP templates** are available, and most of them are designed to fulfil the requirements of Horizon 2020 funding. However, these templates may be used in any research project because they help researchers to consider how data will be managed from the beginning of the project. Planning data management will save time, protect information and increase the impact of research outcomes. The Consortium of University Services of Catalonia (CSUC) has developed an online tool to generate a DMP that can be very useful⁶.

The DMP should ensure that the relevant data in the project is **“FAIR”**: **findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable**. Even though research data can have a broader definition, these principles are mainly applicable to digital data.

⁶<https://dmp.csuc.cat/>

The article published in *Scientific Data* journal, entitled *The Fair Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship*⁷, provides a detailed discussion of the FAIR principles, which are briefly described below:

- Data should be **identified** by a standard identification mechanism (persistent and unique identifiers such as DOI) and described using enough metadata.
- Data should be **stored** in such a way that they can be easily accessed using standardized communication protocols.
- Data should be **structured** in such a way that can be exchanged, reused and combined with other data sets.
- Data should be clearly **licensed** to permit as much data reuse as possible.

Keep in mind that FAIR data are not necessarily equivalent to open data. Researchers can apply restrictions to data access for privacy, security or intellectual property issues. However, all data should be managed and stored in line with FAIR principles.

At the end of the project, researchers should decide which data are useful for the community and should be preserved and shared. Following good research practices, **data underlying publications** are usually made available. However, additional data that are not directly linked to publications (for instance, the so-called negative results) can also be a valuable resource and may deserve to be deposited in a repository.

To **choose a repository for research data**, first check whether a specific database for your discipline or scientific community already exists. Also, all public Catalan universities host an institutional repository to be used by their research staff, and a growing number of commercial publishers offer authors an option to store the research data underlying their publications. Finally, some generic repositories, such as Zenodo⁸, accept data and publications from all disciplines.

⁷ <https://www.nature.com/articles/sdata201618>

⁸ <https://zenodo.org/>

According to the recommendations by CSUC⁹, the following criteria should be considered when choosing a repository:

- Data formats accepted.
- Size of the files accepted.
- Options to restrict access (embargo, restrictions to access data sets).
- Options for licencing data sets.
- Permanent identifier used.
- Costs associated to data archiving and preservation.
- Possibilities to link data to publications.
- Policies for long-term data preservation.
- Options to store different versions of files.
- Fulfilling of funders' requirements.

You can use the registry of research data repositories **re3data** to find the most appropriate repository for your project¹⁰. You can also seek for advice from the experts in data management in your institution.

Metadata

Metadata is information about the research data to allow others to find and reuse these data. Metadata should be structured following a standard format, which may be specific for the discipline or generic. To choose the most appropriate metadata standard for your research data, check the directory provided by the Research Data Alliance¹¹.

⁹<http://hdl.handle.net/2072/362618>

¹⁰<https://re3data.org/>

¹¹<http://rd-alliance.github.io/metadata-directory/standards/>

4. Acknowledging and reporting

4.1 Acknowledging

According to the terms of Beatriu de Pinós call, fellows must **acknowledge the funding received** in all the project results and communication materials. These include scientific publications, data sets in repositories, conference presentations, press releases, website contents, blog posts, infographics, videos, brochures and reports, among others. A formula that might be used to acknowledge funding is provided below as an example:

'Fellow name/This project' has received funding from the postdoctoral fellowships programme Beatriu de Pinós, funded by the Secretary of Universities and Research (Government of Catalonia) and by the Horizon 2020 programme of research and innovation of the European Union under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 801370.

The funding reference should be in the same language of the publication or the material.

Besides, wherever is possible, the communication or dissemination material must display the **EU flag** and the **emblem of the Ministry of Economy and Knowledge of the Government of Catalonia**, which can be downloaded from BP website¹².

Fellows and host institutions can use the **BP visual identity** without first obtaining approval from AGAUR, if its use is associated with activities or results related to the BP grant. In other cases, ask about the conditions by writing an email to BP.postdoc.agaur@gencat.cat.

¹²<http://agaur.gencat.cat/en/Beatriu-de-Pinos/el-programa/identitat-visual/index.html>

4.2 Reporting of communication and dissemination activities

Beatriu de Pinós fellows must keep a record of all the communication and dissemination activities done, and include them in the **mid-term and final reports of the BP grant**. Besides, it is highly recommended that fellows write a Data Management Plan at the beginning of their research project. The information required in the justification reports related to communication and dissemination of results is summarized below. For more details, check the templates of these reports in BP website.

- **Mid-term report** (one month before the midpoint of the grant): scientific publications (including the DOI and the link to the open access repository in which they are deposited), conference presentations, communication and dissemination activities, Data Management Plan.
- **Final report** (two months after the finalisation of the grant): scientific publications (including the DOI and the link to the open access repository in which they are deposited), conference presentations, communication and dissemination activities, knowledge transference and impact of the research project.

BP fellows must inform the BP team at AGAUR as soon as possible about major results published and about communication activities with a **significant impact in the media**.

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5. Final reminders

- **Plan** the communication and dissemination actions of your research project in advance in order to increase impact and visibility.
- Be aware of the **RRI and Open Science** principles encouraged by the European Commission.
- Participate in the **outreach events** organised by your host institution and use the **communication channels** of Beatriu de Pinós programme.
- In peer-reviewed publications, **acknowledge the funding** by the Beatriu de Pinós programme and the European Union, and deposit the final papers in **open access repositories** (preferably OpenAire compatible).
- Create a **Data Management Plan** to make your research data FAIR.
- **Inform the Beatriu de Pinós team** as soon as possible about major results published and communication activities with a major impact in the media.

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6. References and further information

1. Making the Most of Your H2020 Project. Boosting the impact of your project through effective communication, dissemination and exploitation. *The European IPR Helpdesk*. 2018. <https://www.iprhelpdesk.eu/IP-Highlights/brochure>
2. Communicating EU research and innovation guidance for project participants. *European Commission*. 2014. http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/other/gm/h2020-guide-comm_en.pdf
3. Communicating your research. *European Research Council*. <https://erc.europa.eu/managing-your-project/communicating-your-research>
4. Outreach and Communication Activities in the MSCA under Horizon 2020. *European Commission*. https://ec.europa.eu/research/mariecurieactions/resources/document-libraries/guidelines-your-outreach-activities_en
6. European Charter for Researchers. *EURAXESS*. <https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/jobs/charter/european-charter>
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9. Open access & Data management – H2020 Online Manual. *European Commission*. https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/cross-cutting-issues/open-access-dissemination_en.htm
10. OpenAIRE Research Data Management Briefing paper. Understanding Research Data Management. *OpenAIRE*. <https://www.openaire.eu/briefpaper-rdm-infonoads>
11. Open Research Data and Data Management Plans. Information for ERC grantees. *ERC Scientific Council*. V. 3.1, 2019. <https://erc.europa.eu/content/open-research-data-and-data-management-plans-information-erc-grantees>
12. Recomanacions per seleccionar un repositori per al dipòsit de dades de Recerca. *Consorci de Serveis Universitaris de Catalunya (CSUC)*. V.4, 2019. <https://recercat.cat//handle/2072/284974>
13. Guiding you in Open Science. *OpenAIRE*. <https://www.openaire.eu/guides>

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Annex: List of OpenAire compatible institutional repositories in Catalonia for publications

- * Recercat. Dipòsit de la Recerca de Catalunya: <https://www.recercat.cat/>
- * Dipòsit Digital de la Universitat de Barcelona: <http://diposit.ub.edu/dspace/>
- * Dipòsit digital de documents de la UAB: <https://ddd.uab.cat/>
- * UPCommons. Portal de coneixement obert de la UPC: <https://upcommons.upc.edu/>
- * e-Repository UPF: <https://repositori.upf.edu/>
- * RIUVIC. Repositori institucional de la UVic: <http://repositori.uvic.cat/>
- * Repositori Obert UdL: <https://repositori.udl.cat/>
- * Repositori institucional URV: <http://repositori.urv.cat/ca/>
- * DUGiDocs. Repositori Digital de la UdG: <https://dugi-doc.udg.edu/>
- * L'Oberta en Obert. Repositori UOC: <http://openaccess.uoc.edu/>
- * Scientia. Dipòsit d'Informació Digital del Departament de Salut: <https://scientiasalut.gencat.cat/>
- * IRTA Pubpro: <http://repositori.irta.cat/>
- * Digital CSIC: <http://digital.csic.es/>
- * Dipòsit Digital EINA: <https://diposit.eina.cat/>
- * Revistes Catalanes amb Accés Obert: <https://www.raco.cat/>

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